

HISTORY OF UZBEKISTAN AND CHINESE AFFAIRS, TODAY

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Abstract: The article briefly describes the political, economic, cultural relations between China and Uzbekistan, the history of their formation, and the current stages of development.

Key words: Economy, technological issues, diplomacy, partner.

It must be admitted that in recent years a new page has been opened in the history of relations between the two countries. Therefore, it is very important for our country to develop mutually beneficial cooperation with China, which is considered one of the powerful countries of the 21st century, in the political, economic, trade, scientific and cultural spheres.

If we look at history, we can see that in the first days of our independence, that is, on December 27, 1991, the People's Republic of China recognized the independence of the Republic of Uzbekistan, and on January 2, 1992, diplomatic relations were established between the two countries. In October 1992, the embassy of the PRC opened in Tashkent, and in May 1995, the embassy of Uzbekistan opened in Beijing. In recent years, this cooperation has reached a new level of quality.

China is paying special attention to the development of a mutually beneficial and multifaceted relationship with Uzbekistan in its foreign policy. Further strengthening of the partnership is of particular importance in the development of Uzbekistan's relations with Southeast Asian countries.

Uzbekistan-China relations are characterized by rapid development, a solid legal framework, a broad organizational structure and active contacts at all levels.

Especially since 2017, mutual relations have reached a new level in terms of quality. During this period, the leaders of the two countries met 21 times, 3 times last year alone. This shows that the existing ties are getting stronger.

The share and importance of China in the development of the modern world is increasing. Today, this country ranks second among economically developed countries after the United States. Reaching such a level is also related to the demographic factor, that is, the large number of people, the vastness of the territory, and the location on the ocean coast. Uzbekistan's relations with China are also clearly improving. For example, in recent years, the number of Chinese investments in our country has increased by 5 times, and the number of our joint ventures with this country has increased by 3 times. In 11 months of 2023, trade and economic relations worth about 11 billion dollars were registered. Currently, two thousand enterprises established with the participation of Chinese capital are working in our country. This is a serious indicator. Uzbek entrepreneurs and production enterprises are also operating on a large scale in China. In particular, relations in the fields of agriculture, advanced technologies, and innovation are increasing. Now, China has made great progress in forming a new economy using innovative technologies, especially artificial intelligence. Further development of bilateral communication in these areas is urgent.

Uzbekistan has its own national content in the global information space, especially from the news distributed by electronic mass media. After all, the current topic of the day - Uzbekistan - China relations, is widely discussed in articles and news all over the world, especially in China. Materials devoted to bilateral relations, based on the number of the population, closely familiarize the audience of 2 billion people with the reforms being implemented in our country. The whole world knows about us. Developed countries of the world, European and Asian countries are also receiving information about Uzbekistan.

As Xi Jinping wrote, “China and Uzbekistan are ancient countries with a great civilization. The Great Silk Road is a symbol of friendly relations between our

peoples for more than 2000 years. Uzbekistan is a large country located in the heart of Central Asia. It should be noted separately that under the leadership of President Shavkat Mirziyoyev, the Uzbek people have embarked on a great path towards the establishment of New Uzbekistan. The pace of reforms and development in various fields has accelerated. The country got a completely new look, the position of the republic in the international arena was significantly strengthened. As a sincere friend and comprehensive strategic partner, we are delighted with your success.

Earlier, when we thought of China, only Chinese porcelain came to mind. In recent years, due to the wise policy of the leaders of the two countries, the process of comprehensive strategic partnership has reached a high level. The "One Place, One Way" project is creating a foundation for strengthening the bond of eternal friendship and ensuring that it reaches from generation to generation. China is also one of Uzbekistan's closest partners in the field of education.

Chinese language is included in the list of 8 priority foreign languages in the field of national education. Today is the country of ChinTashkentState Oriental Studies, State World Languages of Uzbekistan, Universities of World Economy and Diplomacy,NamanganInstitute of Engineering and Technology,Bukharahas been officially cooperating with 18 higher educational institutions like the state university. Two Confucius Institutes have been closely familiarizing Uzbeks with the Chinese language and culture. Uzbek language teaching has been started at China Central University of Nations and Beijing Foreign Languages University. A separate department of the Uzbek language operates at the Shanghai International Studies University, which is considered one of the prestigious academic institutions. In accordance with the bilateral agreement and within the framework of the SCO, the government of the People's Republic of China regularly allocates grants to students and interns from Uzbekistan.

In general, relations between Uzbekistan and China are developing effectively within the framework of the SCO. For example, Uzbekistan has rightfully taken its place among the prestigious international organizations and has become an

influential factor in sustainable development, strengthening peace, combating modern threats and dangers, and ensuring security at the regional and global level. In a word, the current state of relations is a proof that our countries are long-term strategic partners with each other. The most important thing is that this situation fully corresponds to the national interest of the peoples of the two countries, as well as the requirements of the present time. The dialogue between the two countries is of great importance in the history of consistently developing international relations and paves the way for achieving more effective results.

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